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Abstract-

In the Indian Constitution, women have been given the right to equality of opportunities, but these rights are not reaching women. At present, the area of industrialization is increasing in rural areas and industries have knocked outside the villages. In such a situation, new means of employment have opened up for the women of rural areas, but along with this the means of their exploitation have also opened up. Economic exploitation of women takes place due to cheap labour, unorganized labour. Rural women have already played a role in the economic sector. Apart from farming and animal husbandry, it used to do Gajdoori but its role was never recognized but now due to industrialization its role is being recognized.

Introduction-

After the establishment of the British rule in medieval India, the society moves from the feudal age to the industrial age. In this era, the expansion of industries began. Instead of hand, production was done on a large scale by machines. The factory production process started. The cumulative result of all this was that women began to participate less and less in production. As long as the production of goods was done by hand, women's participation in it was relatively high, but when the production started in the factories through machines, it became difficult for the women to leave their traditional work and go to work in the factories. At the same time, the production process of industrial society developed and specialized and required special training. Such training was difficult for women to obtain by breaking social norms and restrictions. Because of this also the participation of women in the industrial economy became extremely limited and narrow.

After independence, new dimensions of women's economic participation have expanded in India. On the one hand, the constitution has theoretically abolished the inequality on the basis of gender by providing the right to equality, on the other hand many special programs have been adopted for the development program, especially for the educational and economic development of women. These programs have resulted in substantial increase in additional employment opportunities. Therefore, after independence, women got a new environment for economic power and independence.

It is known from various studies that the economic participation of those women is found to be relatively high whose economic level of the family is found to be relatively low. It is well known that in every country economic activities are differentiated on two grounds - unorganized and organized.

organized -

In the organized sector, the trade of the industry is done on a wider scale, but not on a wider scale in the unorganized sector. In the unorganized sector, there is a lack of labor unions and laws protecting the interests of the workers, as in the organized sector. Since labor unions are either absent or inactive in the unorganized sector, the workers in this sector do not get this favorable bargaining opportunity, which is available to the workers in the organized sector. A large number

of women workers are employed in the unorganized sector. Traditionally, a significant portion of the female workforce in Indian society has been engaged in the agriculture sector and mainly in family-centred industries such as small-scale manufacturing, food items manufacturing or other small jobs such as beedi making, sewing laces of clothes, making incense sticks etc. The number of women is found to be more than men in sugarcane industry, spinning yarn, making jute goods, coffee making, rope making, silkworm rearing, butter, ghee. Jain, pickle, jelly, papad have to be made.

unorganized

Unorganized sector is unsafe sector for women, in this they have to work more hard work but labor rewards and productivity but longer duration. Under the Indian economic and industrial structure, most of the industries are not in the organized sector but in the unorganized sector. It is known on the basis of study that development programs also encourage such economic activities which are expanding the employment opportunities of the unorganized sector. The personal benefit of the entrepreneur is also in this, but he should do the work of production in the unorganized sector because in this sector there is less interference of the laws like Factory Act, Labor Act etc. and on the other hand it is time to take more work for less wages. This is known through studies. that the supply of female labor is determined by the level of family income and not by the rate of wages Since most of the female workers enter because of low family income, they accept any type of work and any rate of wages . By analyzing the economic system of women in the unorganized sector, two conclusions have been rendered from the point of view of social justice and policy making.

1. 1. An increasingly increasing proportion of the population is living on the frontier.
2. 2. Low wage labor is available in the unorganized sector, so the entrepreneur does most of his economic activities in such areas.

The result of this is that these women workers are not getting any special benefit from the process of economic development. This situation is not only detrimental to the status of women but is also making the process of economic development unbalanced.

According to the 2011 census, 29.9 million people are working in Rajasthan, out of which 18.3 million are men and 11.6 million are women. The important fact in this is that 10.6 million women work in rural areas and only 0.98 million women work in urban areas. Thus, 77 percent of the total rural female labor force and 18 percent of the urban female labor force work in agriculture and allied activities in villages. Urban women are less in number but mostly employed in organized sector where their wages are higher than rural women workers. Some of the major studies done to know the socio-economic status of rural women, such as Gulati 1975, Bolkia and Dholakia 1978, Barchan 1979 and Dasgupta 2005, found that the education of working women and their work is having a negative impact on their children. The number of women workers is increasing in both rural and urban areas. Barghan found that the number of women workers belonging to Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes is increasing more in rural areas. Very few such state level studies have been done in India, some of the states in which this type of study has been done are Kerala, West Bengal and Uttar Pradesh, this study was done by I. Chakraborty in 2010. It found that there is a gender disparity in income facts in West Bengal. And less educated women work as laborers in large numbers. The work of

Muslim women as labor is very high. Nominee P.K. concluded in 2013 in their article Female Work Participation in: Uttar Pradesh: Trade and Determinants that the sex ratio and the number of castes in the workforce are increasing more. The reason for this was their less education.

In Rajasthan, there has been a decrease of 146 percent in the number of women farmers in the last decade and there has been a percentage increase in the number of women agricultural laborers. The number of women workers in organized sectors has increased by 03 percent. In the last decade, the total number of female workers in Rajasthan has increased by 6.7 percent. Population percentage of total rural female workers in Rajasthan - 34.7 percent

Contribution of rural women to total workforce in Rajasthan - 42.7 percent

Contribution of rural women to total labor force in Rajasthan - 34.9 percent

Number of rural women workers (15 years and above) on 1000 people - 411

Percentage of self-employed rural women -76.5 percent,

Percentage of rural women who are regular workers/wage earners - 2.6 percent

The percentage of daily wage rural women workers is 21 percent

Percentage of unemployed rural women in Rajasthan 1- 0.7 percent

Number of rural unemployed females per 1000 people (15 years and above) 16

Percentage of employed and unemployed rural women workers in Rajasthan: 20% employed, 27% unemployed

Average income of rural women - Rs 177.86 per day

The income of rural women laborers who work on daily wages is Rs 118.57 per day

Composition of female workers in Rajasthan as per 2011 census

	Total	Rural	urban
Total Workers	35.1	42.7	12.0
key workers	50.2	48.7	42.6
marginal worker	49.8	51.9	27.4
Farmer	52.6	56.6	9.4
agricultural laborer	24.2	25.6	8.8
organized sector labor	2.2	1.9	8.8
other	20.7	15.8	73.0

Composition of Women Workers in Rajasthan 2001-2011

year	2001			2011		
	Total	Rural	urban	Total	Rural	urban
total labor participation Percent						
Farmer	67.0	70.7	14.7	52.6	56.6	9.4
unorganized and agricultural laborers	16.2	16.8	6.9	24.2	25.6	8.8
organized sector	2.8	2.1	13.6	2.5	1.9	8.8
other workers	14.0	10.4	64.8	20.7	15.8	73.0

Source - PCA Chapter 4 I and II, Census of India 2011

The total geographical area of India is 328.7 million hectares, of which the reported area is 305.9 million hectares. According to the Ministry of Agriculture, the area under cultivation in 2011 was 141.6 million hectares. In the year 1971 it was 14.09 crore hectare. The study of the report of the Department of Agriculture shows that in the last 50 years, the decrease in the area sown is only around 14 crore hectares. The Central Agriculture Department estimates the area under cultivation, not by directly counting it, but by projecting it only on the basis of reports received from the states over the years. Certainly this area of the total land is not correct. Unfortunately, all the schemes related to agriculture in the country have been made on the basis of this.

Agricultural land has been estimated in 2013 through a sample survey. According to the Sample Survey 2013 'Family Ownership and Self-Owned Holdings', 11.74 crore hectares of land was owned by households living in rural India in 1992. In the year 2013, it has decreased to 9.24 crore hectare. That is, in 20 years, 250 million hectares of land has decreased in the ownership of families in rural India. From 1992 to 2013, agricultural land in rural India decreased by 21 percent. Due to increasing population and shrinking land, the average land area per household has decreased rapidly. According to the Sample Survey 2013, the average land holding per household in rural India was 1.01 hectares in 1992, which has reduced to 0.59 hectares per household in 2013. If we estimate it on the basis of the total number of families in the country, then the average land per family is 0.37 hectare.

The incidence of total cultivated land and average cultivated land per household is a matter of concern for agrarian India. Even today the country is not self-sufficient in food grains. Agricultural produce has to be imported. The total cultivated area of the country is not enough to meet the food requirement of the country and the average cultivated area is not enough to feed a family. But the government is not worried about the adverse effects on the country due to the reduction of agricultural land due to the attack on the agricultural land, instead of improving the country's policies, the policy makers are looking for a solution to the crisis in industrialization. For that industrial corridor, corporate farming and smart city construction have been planned.

Delhi Mumbai Industrial as a global manufacturing and trading hub in India. Work has begun to develop the corridor, which will include industrial areas, expansion of existing industrial areas, ports, modern airports, special economic zones, industrial parks, IT, ITES, biotech hubs and agro-processing hubs, smart cities, integrated townships, infrastructure facilities. Power plants, expansion of national and state highways, dedicated freight corridors, high-speed rail-road transport network, etc. will be built.

The Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor is 1483 kms. length and about 300 km. width is being developed over an area of 4.36 crore hectares. According to the report, it covers 150 to 200 sq. kms. There will be 9 industrial zones. There is a plan to make 6 industrial corridors in India. The total length of 5 corridors affecting 16 states of the country, except the North East Myanmar Corridor, is 6.749 km and the total affected land area comes to 201.4 million hectares. Which is 66 percent of the reported land area of the country. for any project. How much land is required is given in the project report but it is not clear in the project report of Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor. The total land that will be required is being deliberately hidden. On the basis of estimation, even if 20 percent land of the total affected area is taken for all the corridors, it still amounts to 40 million hectares of land. Apart from this, the area of other projects being built in the country will be additional.

Farming land has become real estate business for the wealthy. Almost most of the land on the periphery of any small or big city has now gone to the wealthy. Agriculture has been made a source of investment. Farm house, agriculture, tourism has taken the form of a business for them. It has become a way to digest black money. The encroachment on agricultural land has increased for the expansion of cities. A class of brokers and moneylenders has become ready in the country to snatch the land of the farmers who are facing economic crisis. Most of the facilities and schemes that are available to the farmers are now getting the same by conniving with the officials. 100 smart cities are being built in the country to create a separate world for the rich. Due to increasing urbanization, cities are expanding rapidly. The encroachment on agricultural land has increased for the expansion of smart cities and towns.

Talking about reducing the burden of farming, the government is working on a plan to remove farmers from farming and keep their number to 20 percent. Allowing foreign investment in agriculture, encouraging capital and technology, contract farming, corporate farming, all these are part of the same plan. Here, to fulfill the conditions of the World Trade Organization, there is a plan to do farming for the world market, in which, in the future, cultivation of flowers, cultivation of organic fuel etc. will come to overcome the crisis of fuel shortage. In India, the failed Israeli method of farming has started again. All fertile farming will be handed over to companies for corporate farming. According to the plan of corporate farming, land will be snatched from all the farmers of the country and cultivated by 20 percent big corporate farmers. It seems that the government wants to grow the crop of death, not life-giving grains in the country.

Crores of hectares of agricultural land will be snatched away from the farmers for non-agriculture work and for corporate farming on the rest of the land in the country for industrial area corridors, real estate, new cities and city expansion etc. The government is claiming to do all this work for the benefit of the farmers. For a long time, the work of looting the farmers in the name of the cream of the farmers is going on. If these plans were successful then it was estimated. It can be estimated that out of 9.24 crore hectares of cultivated land, at least 4 crore hectares of land will be out of cultivation. The country will be left with only 5 crore hectares of agricultural land and the average land area per household will be 0.25 hectares in rural India and 0.17 hectares i.e. 18000 square feet of agricultural land for the country based on the total number of families. The average land area for one person will be 3600 square feet.

There was once 14 crore hectares of agricultural land in the country. Now only 9.24 hectares is left. In 4-5 decades, about 5 crore hectares i.e. 34 percent of the cultivated land has decreased. The pace of industrialization and all-round attack on agriculture has further intensified. Government is very serious about snatching the land of the farmers. That's why it has not stopped only by making plans, but (as per the convenience of the companies) is changing the land related policy and laws.

Land Acquisition Act 1894 was changed under the pressure of corporates. But due to the awareness of the mass movements, the corporates could not make it completely favorable to them. Despite the opposition of the public, the work of changing it in favor of the companies is being done continuously. Laws and regulations have been changed in many states to enable companies to buy land directly from farmers.

The Land Ceiling Act is not being followed for the companies. Rather, efforts are being made to change it, so that companies can occupy

unlimited land. Changes have been made in the Urban Ceiling Act. The demand has been raised in many places in the country to enact a law to give back the land to the farmers for the schemes for which the land has been acquired, but the government does not want to enact such a law. Land banks have been created for additional land acquired for projects, so that land can be easily transferred to companies. Overall, the government has taken up the task of ruining the farmers of the country by snatching their land for the corporates who give the rulers a ton of money. Here the official report and D.M.I. C. On the basis of the report, an attempt has been made to bring out the picture of the loot of agricultural land so that we can explain a terrible reality. But it will not be entirely clear based on mere conjecture. The people of this country have every right to know and the Government of India should make it clear that since 1991 till date, how much agricultural land has been used or acquired for non-agricultural purposes and how much is available with the country today. There is agricultural land. Along with this, the government should also make it clear that on the basis of the project report, how much land is required for the above schemes made in the name of development and what will be its effect on the farmers and agriculture of the country. That's why direct counting of agricultural land should be done. The government should issue a white paper to place the land related facts in front of the country. At the same time, people's movements will also have to fight for the Agricultural Land Protection Act, if not for the reform of the Land Acquisition Act.

Even today more than 60 percent people in the country get employment from agriculture. Farming is the only means of livelihood and employment left for the farmers. It also provides employment to landless farmers. There is no such sector in the world, in which employment can be created on such a large scale. To satisfy the hunger of the farmers for themselves and the country. The role of farmers and agriculture is important for the food, clothing, housing, food security of the people of the country and also for the security of the country. Due to industrialization, the total cultivated land and the average cultivated land per family are rapidly decreasing, on the other hand, climate change and global warming are adversely affecting agriculture. Due to climate change, global temperature rise, agricultural production will decrease by 20 percent.

Need to study the role of women

The first socio-economic study on women workers was conducted by the Labor Bureau in 1953, whose report was titled 'The Economic and Social Status of Women's Work in India'. It included women workers in the cotton and jute textile, coal mines and plantation industries. After this, the Labor Bureau and the Planning Commission jointly conducted a study in 1958 'Deegan in Employment 1901-1956'. The first report of this study came in the name of 'Women in Employment' in 1964, followed by 'Began in Industry' in 1975. In these reports, the facts related to the employment of women workers such as income, conscious laws, working conditions and the acts applicable in employment were studied. In 1975 the complete study Socio-Economic Conditions of Women's Work was published. In which the living conditions of women workers were told. It was also found that most of the female labor is employed in the unorganized sector. About 90 percent of the female labor is working in the unorganized sectors. The first study in the mine area was done in 1976-77. After this, the Labor Bureau got 23 surveys done on the economic and social status of women workers, in which the matchbox industry was also included.

The rural working woman is becoming economically capable and her status in the society is getting higher. An economically empowered woman is creating a empowered family. The roles of women in the family are being

restructured. The growing confidence of women along with education and skill development is ending evils like dowry system, child marriage in the society and the society is getting a new direction of change. The role of industrialization has been more important in the social and economic advancement of women. Industrialization has not only brought economic growth but also increased women empowerment, provided economic empowerment to women and brought changes in the society. This research becomes important to understand these changes and industrialization and the role of women in the present context.

Study problem: -

India is a village dominated country. The status of women in rural Indian societies has been considered negligible. In such a situation, the problems of child marriage, female feticide, dowry system, purdah system, sati system, girl child illiteracy, violence against women etc. are prevailing in the rural society.

New laws were made to protect women for their economic, social and political rights, as well as industrialization has also led to the economic advancement of women. Under the labor law, women workers were provided maternity leave, child rearing time, travel facilities, etc. Despite so many reforms, has there been any improvement in the backward social, economic and political conditions of women workers in the last decades? Has there been any change in the social status of women? Are women of this class getting enough support from their industrial owners, organizations, government laws, schemes? Has the labor law proved to be effective in improving the condition of women workers of this class, has the skill and income of women workers developed in the last decades. Keeping all these issues in view, the need was felt to know the real situation by studying the current situation of rural women workers. Discrimination against social justice, backward, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and women etc. is a growing problem in rural areas and this problem can be solved only when government schemes and laws are implemented effectively. The current labor law has improved the status of women workers but the condition of women workers in the unorganized sector is still very bad. Along with their economic condition, physical condition, health condition is also bad. In such a situation, it is necessary to find out the real situation by comparing women workers of unorganized and organized sectors so that in future good plans can be made for women workers and their condition can be improved. Similarly, to what extent do the industrial organizations work for the welfare of the youth, does it follow the norms of youth and working conditions, facilities, pay leave fixed by the government or not? Finding out its real status has also been a major requirement of this study.

Limitations that may affect the conclusion of the research-

1. The present research has been done on rural women. The presence of a male member at the time of compilation of facts may lead to compilation of wrong facts.
2. This study is based on rural labor women who mainly work under contractor or masseur. The influence of the contractor or the owner in the compilation of facts may also lead to error in facts.
3. Rural environment and local language can also create problems in connecting reliably with rural labor women.

Objectives of the study -

Apart from being an important part of the population of a country, the working class is also an important human resource for national

development. From this point of view, the study of family structure of industrial workers is very important. From the family structure and functions of the workers. The changes taking place can be influenced by sociological study and discussion on the family environment of the workers which plays a decisive role in their socialization.

Main objectives of the research -

1. To find out the socio-economic conditions of rural labor women.
2. To find out the role of rural labor women in economic progress.
3. To find out the economic, social, family changes in rural labor women after working.
4. To find out the impact of industrialization on rural women.
5. To find out the relationship between industrialization and economic potential of women

Field of study -

For the present study, Rajasthan's major industrial units, small and large scale industries, Int Bhatos have been selected as the study area. Industrial development in Rajasthan-

- ❖ Export Promotion & Industrial Park
- ❖ Special Economic Zone

Project -

Research is the scientific study of social phenomena and no study can be scientific unless the scientific method is used in it. The hypothesis is related to the purpose of research, so the researcher does not only determine the objectives or goals of the research through the hypothesis, but also discusses the facts related to the study area, working relationships, etc. Finally, the hypothesis is considered a link between research and theory.

1. Industrialization has led to the exploitation of rural women as cheap labour.
2. Social facts create obstacles in the implementation of schemes for the upliftment of rural women.
3. Industrialization has led to socio-economic advancement of rural women.
4. Contribution of rural women in economic progress is increasing.

conclusion -

At present, the domestic status of the working women has been included in the social and economic life aspects of the working women. In this the conclusion was presented that the domestic status of working women is comparatively better than that of non-working women. The reason for this is that working women are financially capable. For this reason, the opinion of working women is important in the economic aspects of the house because working women also contribute in the economic aspects of the household.

Gender biased aspects in social life Gender biased at domestic and professional levels of working women It was found that gender biased is still done with working women but its level has reduced to a great extent. Labour: Women work at the same professional level as men and with equal efficiency, but unskilled women workers are discriminated against

in terms of income. Women employed in brick kilns and small scale industrial units get less wages than men. On the other hand, skilled women in medium and high industrial units get the same salary as men.

At the domestic level, gender discrimination was less observed with women workers. Women have the freedom to come and go to work, to keep and spend their money alone.

With reference to the reasons for women to work, it was found that most of the women have to work as unskilled labor due to poor family conditions. On the other hand, the reason for the work of skilled women is their education, training and cooperation of family members. Skilled women workers are moving out of rural areas to work in hospitals, factories and factories in urban areas. This is a sign of their empowerment.

In the social life of working women, they get more freedom to take decisions. She takes this decision on her marriage, education of her children etc. Along with this, self-reliance is also found more in them. Working women are equally alert in domestic work. Working women do not only do business work, but also do all the work of cooking, washing utensils, washing clothes, cleaning in their homes. Sometimes they get help from other female and male members of their family in these works but it is clear. That working women have to play a dual role.

In the schemes of economic development operated in the context of women, study was done in the context of Bhamashah Yojana, Self Help Group and Kaushal Vikas Yojana. It is clear from this study that these schemes are making women financially capable to some extent. In Bhamashah Yojana, the woman is recognized as the head of her family and government assistance comes in her own bank account. Due to which the economic condition of women has improved. She can use this government help according to herself but this is not the case with all women right now. Due to family pressure, she spends this financial assistance according to the family members.

Usefulness of research in future

The clear effect of industrialization, modernization, globalization can be seen on the social, economic, cultural structure of the villages. The combined effect of all this is visible in terms of increase in rural utilization level. The demand for consumer goods and services is continuously increasing in rural areas. This increasing demand has also increased new employment opportunities in the villages. The future of villages seems to be filled with immense possibilities of employment. There is a need to raise the level of rural participation in the national economy through its better regulation, driven management.

The usefulness of the research is evident from the following points-

1. This research plays a remarkable role in the direction of women empowerment, it will help in making plans to make women financially capable and build their skills.
2. Explains the status of women workers in unorganized sectors. This study is useful in improving the condition of unorganized sectors.
3. This study explains the background of amendment in labor laws.
4. The study clarifies the social, economic and political development of women workers especially women from rural background. This study gives proper direction towards the empowerment of women.

Challenges and Solutions-

With new possibilities, there is no dearth of challenges in rural areas. Without dealing with these, we cannot imagine rural employment generation and its betterment.

Teaching-Training-

The biggest challenge is education and training. We are still stuck with the traditional educational system whereas in modern times the demand for vocational education is gaining momentum. Our education system is not able to prepare better labor force for modern employment. In rural areas, most of the people get primary and few people get secondary education. But this education is not specialized. Our efforts should be towards adopting vocational-oriented teaching method from primary in rural areas.

Apart from this, alternative training should be arranged for illiterate people. Efforts will have to be made for teaching-training for industrial training, training for non-agricultural works, skill development required for employment related to information technology, service sector etc.

energy availability

The biggest obstacle in the path of new industry, production unit or rural industrialization is the availability of energy. Despite rural electrification schemes, still 25 percent villages are not fully electrified. Electrification is still awaited in about 1.15 lakh villages in 20 states. The way of rural industrialization is opening for rural employment, but it is a big challenge from the point of view of energy availability. We have to be serious about increasing the dependence of such villages on alternate sources of energy. For this, the spread of alternatives like solar energy, wind energy should be accelerated.

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